

**COSMIC ABSURDITY IN THOMAS HARDY'S RETURN OF THE
NATIVE**

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Abstract:

Thomas Hardy (OM), the last of the great Victorians, contemporary of the events of two centuries (the second half of the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century), and chiefly famous for his tragic novels—even though his other novels which are not tragic such as romances and fantasies as well as novels of ingenuity can't be undermined—such as *Tess of the d'Urbervilles: A Pure Woman Faithfully Presented*, *The Mayor of Casterbridge: The Life and Death of A Man Of Character*, *Jude The Obscure* (Originally entitled as *The Simpletons Hearts Insurgent*), and *The Return of The native*— is oft' known as an 'Extentionalist' (writer) for his novels and verses as well have directly or indirectly the traces of the existential thought. They are brimming with existential themes, characters, concepts and crises. They have the traces of angst, dread, despair, authenticity, facticity, The Other and the Look, cosmic absurdity, and existence preceding essence. He, like Earnest Hemingway, W.H. Auden, James Baldwin, and Samuel Beckett, is highly affected by the thought of this so called school—for the thinkers and the writers of this 'ism' belong to distant countries of distant ages. Present article tries to trace out the existential concept of cosmic absurdity in *The Return of the Native* through the textual analysis of the related literature along with descriptive and explorative approaches. Additionally, it will try to define existentialism mentioning its chief masters, and the chief concepts in short, but the cosmic absurdity in detail. Existential questions which directly or indirectly cause cosmic absurdity will also be included in this article.

Keywords:

Cosmic Absurdity, Existence, Essence, Acne, Paronoma, Melodist, Sentience

Thomas Hardy is one of the greatest Victorian novelists of the second half of 19th century, and a so called minor poet—as he was not a minor poet for the corpus his verses are its witness— of the first half of 20th century in the realm of English literature. By virtue, he is a maestro of a very high order with a brilliant and insightful corpus of fictions, with unique and penetrating impressions of poems, with a professional training in architect, and with a few unsung paintings. Over all, his topnotch literariness enthrone him on the throne of the scholars' mind and soul. He is a tragic novelist, a famous moralist, an adept regionalist, an evolutionary *meliorist* rather than pessimist, and a serious visionary with selected provisions. What William Shakespeare, the bard of Avon, has done in the field of tragic plays, Thomas Hardy has done in the field of tragic fictions. Both are cathartic with or without purgation. He is often called the precursor of D.H. Lawrence whose works reflect on modernity, industrialization, sexuality, emotional health, vitality, spontaneity, and instinct. Seriousness of thoughts, subtle directness of narration, subtleties of style, and projection of philosophical vision and provisions make his fictions par excellence. It is another thing that he was an architect by profession; a poet by choice; a novelist by necessity; and a painter by accidental instinct. The deep study of his novels and verses as well interestingly reflect the traces of existentialism— whether it is its themes, or its principles, or its concepts— for it is close to humanism— especially individualism which pays attention to pains and pangs of the individuals. His works embarrass man's self importance manifesting or recommending that man is of no matter or considerable value in this nonchalant cosmos. This is the reason why it is mentioned as he has penned in his various verses besides novels:

He dwells repeatedly on the injustice of uncompensated, needless pain, and on the thought that even our hours of happiness are passing towards nothing— 'when a man falls he lies'; 'the monotonous hours clang negligently by' (A Sign Seeker). Hardy either questions the very existence of a god, be he 'vengeful' or not (Hap), or laments the 'logicless' nature of the workings of the universe (New Years Eve), and the fact that if there is a 'powerfuller than I', he is 'unknowing' (The Bed Ridden Peasant) and 'indifferent' he 'does not care' (At a Bridal)...(*The Wordsworth Poetry Library, The Works of Thomas Hardy viii*).

Hardy's such thoughts bring him close to the existentialists. Like them, he too was unable to see the injustice and indifference done to man. The Wordsworth Poetry Library says: "Indifferences bothered Hardy a great deal, his philosophical bugbear was the apparent amorality of the 'cause' of the things: 'loveless and hateless I have called it, which neither good nor evil knows'" (*The Works of Thomas Hardy viii*). Whatever he observes, he pens. Whatever he pens, he observes. As a laureate of street, he observes each and every huge and minute thing related to each and every individual. It is the very fact which sometimes partially and sometimes fully brings him close to the existentialists and fascinates the eyes of the scholars for exploration.

Roy Morrell in his book *Thomas Hardy: The Will and the Ways*, and David J. De Laura in his article entitled as *The Acne of Modernism in Hardy's Later Novels* successively deal with the problem of human existence and the modern existentialist imagination. When his novels are read between the lines, it is found that they naturally reflect existential stand points such as man's experiences of the cosmic absurdity, feelings of life's meaninglessness, senses of birth's purposelessness, tenses of alienation, and searchings for the self along with the existential conceptual *paronoma* of existence, essence, facticity, authenticity, angst, dread, despair, and the Other and the look owing to which he comes in the queue of existential writers like Jean-Paul Sartre, Soren Kierkegaard, Albert Camus, Friedrich Nietzsche, Simon de Beauvoir, Martin Heidegger, Gabriel Marcel, Karl Jasper, Fyodor Dostoevsky, Paul Tillich. It is another thing that he does not directly belong to this school of thought, but the effect of this so called school, which is seen over him peeping through his works, is par excellence. David Daiches writes:

The novels of Tomas Hardy also show some disparity between genius and achievement, but here the final achievement seems greater, not less, than a critical inspection of the talents at work would seem to warrant, Hardy's irony is not directed at human egotism or at the disparity between real and assumed worth, but at the very conditions of human existence (*A Critical History of English Literature* 1073).

Existentialism, a timeless sensibility for its traces "can be discerned here and there in the past" (*Walter Kaufman* 12), a critic of theoria for criticizing most of the theories related to man, a rejecter of absoluteness of reason for rejecting purely abstract and logical thinking, and an attributor to humanism for focusing on individual's own life and action rather than individual liberty and opportunity, shuns the chimera of abstraction for the concrete analysis of human experiences to study the predicament of human existence without thinking man as an idea or a thing. It is said that "Existential philosophy... has rebelled against the arid technicality of metaphysics, and has brought philosophy closer to living the problem of real life" (*Marjorie Grene* 26). It is a new name of the recent origin (19th and 20th century) for the old philosophy as its traces are found in the Upanishad's of the Hindus and the Scriptures of the Baudhists. Because of it, in the chapter "Concluding Survey" in *The History of Philosophy: Eastern and Western*, it is written that: "Existentialism is a new name for an ancient method" (*Dr. S. Radhakrishnan* 443). Writers like Jean-Paul Sartre, Soren Kierkegaard, Albert Camus, Friedrich Nietzsche, Simon de Beauvoir, Martin Heidegger, Gabriel Marcel, Karl Jasper, Fyodor Dostoevsky, Paul Tillich are its chief hallmarkers. Although these thinkers belong to distant countries of distant ages, there is a similarity among their thoughts with a little difference, they affect the successive writers of distant countries of distant ages of different literature as well. English literature has also been affected by it from time to time. Samuel Beckett, W.H. Auden, Earnest Hemingway

and Thomas Hardy are the chief instances of the existential writers in English literature as their works are brimming with its themes, concepts, and ideologies.

It's impossible to understand existentialism without understanding the existential questions which are deep philosophical enquiries related to the nature of someone or something's existence. Such questions are related to the meaning of life, purpose of birth, identity and freedom of the individual, value of human existence, and the subjective experience of an individual's thinking, feeling, and acting as well. Who am I? What is the meaning of life? What is the purpose of birth? What is the value of human existence? Is there a god? What is death? Why is this cosmos indifference to an individual?—are such queries as have perplexed the existential philosophers and they have done their best to find out their best answer from time to time.

Existentialism is the *Paronoma* of concepts which include “Existence precedes essence” (*Cuddon 295*), existential crisis, facticity, authenticity, the Other and the Look, Angst and dread, despair, and cosmic absurdity etc. Soren Kierkegaard fathered it. Its first central claim is the postulation that existence precedes essence. It is the reversal of the traditional philosophical view which says that the essence of a thing is more fundamental and immutable than its existence, while the second is the existential crisis which is related to the inner conflicts of the individual caused by the meaninglessness of life. Its third concept is facticity which stands for a limitation and condition of individuals' freedom, while the fourth is authenticity which is the process of 'creating oneself' to live in accordance with this self. The fifth concept of it is 'The Other and the Look' which stands for how people judge an individual, and how an individual experiences the world. The concept of angst and dread is the sixth concept of this 'ism'. Generally, it is a negative feeling which arises from the experiences of human freedom and responsibility. Next comes despair which is defined as a loss of hope and faith.

Cosmic Absurdity is one of the chief concepts of existentialism as a whole. It is an amalgam of two words 'Cosmic' and 'Absurdity'. The Word 'Absurdity' comes from the word 'Absurd' which stands for 'Out of tune' or 'Out of harmony,' and accommodates the conception that there is no meaning in this world beyond the meaning that man gives it. Such a type of meaninglessness of the world or cosmos too encloses the “unfairness” of the world. Most of the existentialist writers have defined the term 'Absurd' in their own ways. To Kierkegaard, “the absurdity of religious truths prevent us from reaching God rationality” (*John Foley 5/6*). “Sartre recognizes the absurdity of individual experience” (Wikipedia), and Camus follows his (Sartre's) definition of the Absurd: “That which is meaningless. Thus man's existence is absurd because his contingency finds no external justification” (*John Foley 5/6*). There is confrontation between man and the nature (World/Cosmos). According to Albert Camus: “The world, or the human

being is not in itself absurd. The concept only merges through the juxtaposition of the two; life becomes absurd owing to the incompatibility between human beings and the world they inhabit” (Wikipedia). This view constitutes one of the two interpretations of the absurd in existentialist literature. The second view, first elaborated by Soren Kierkegaard, holds that absurdity is limited to actions and choices of human beings. These are considered absurd since they issue from human freedom, undermining their foundation outside of themselves” (*Stephen Michelman* 27). In other words the fundamental dissonance between man and the universe induces a deep feeling of the absurd in man’s mind. Man pines for order and justice, but gets only the bitter feeling of cosmic absurdity for the nature of the cosmos is disorder and injustice. It always remains indifference to man’s destiny to feel and suffer. It can be described as what about the ‘Nature’ Alfred Lord Tennyson, the representative poet of Victorian Age says: “Tho’ Nature, red in tooth and claw/ With ravine, shriek’d against his creed” (*In Memorium A.H.H. Canto* 56).

The vision of cosmic absurdity is powerfully projected through a few devices such as chance or time and coincidence, irony, natural calamity and accident in the most novels of Thomas Hardy. His most characters ever appear to be in metaphysical quest in such a world which is alien to them besides being full of cares and sufferings. They feel that their existence is useless and is needless without any solid need in this world. They feel to be abandoned, neglected, and thrown in the (fictional) cosmology (of Hardy). The sense of ‘Otherness’ is always buzzing in their mind and heart. Anxiety is brooding on their faces. Angst and dread are shaking their hope and faith. They struggle to get authenticity and facticity, but as it appear all in vain. Hemingway often handle ‘NADA’ which is a Spanish word which symbolizes man’s gloom, frustration, horror and terror, tense, nothingness of passions. What is NADA to Hemingway, Cosmic Absurdity is to Thomas Hardy. Both present the human predicament or existence. Human existence is a paradox which cannot be nearly understood by rational thought. There is no rational solution to the dilemma of human existence and the ways of the cosmos.

Hardy’s novels from the *Desperate Remedies* to *Jude the Obscure* present a clear picture of cosmic absurdity along with the predicament of man’s life significantly. His major tragic fictions as *The Return of the Native*, *The Mayor of Casterbridge*, *Tess of the d’Urbervilles*, and *Jude the Obscure* are ahead in projecting such things. The theme of cosmic absurdity, of man’s will as well as choice and bitter truth at variance is aptly reflected in his both the major and minor fictions as well. *The Return of the Native*, key to Hardy’s mind and art, also precisely deals with the theme of cosmic absurdity. Egdon Heath which is the scenic background to the action of the present fiction, which is an enduring symbol of his (Hardy’s) visions of cosmic power, which symbolizes the cosmic reality in which the individuals long for order and rationality thwarted by its ceaseless indifferences is nothing but a symbol of cosmic power. In it, the absurd situations

mercilessly hold the characters in the hollow of its hand. They are puppet in its cruel hands. Their string is in its hand. What it wants, they do. Through it, Hardy presents his views of man's existence in this cosmos and its ways to man. About it, it is said: "The Heath is the world. So far as the novel is concerned, and has within it, sharply focused and defined all the antimonies and idiosyncrasies of the real, larger world" (*Penelop Vigar* 126). Undoubtedly, it offers the grim and neglected condition of human life and describes the human beings contingencies such as their purposeless birth, their meaningless life, their realization of helplessness and neglect, their feeling of being unwanted and abandoned. They feel to be thrown in a 'quandary' with a sense of trial and insignificant existence. To them, Egdon Heath, a metaphysical landscape with dark soil, is a hostile power which makes them playthings—plays with them as it likes—and brings havoc in their lives through hostile interferences. The whole novel shows that life is eventually small, commonplace, and futile. To Hardy, it (Egdon Heath) has a personality of cosmic indifferences. He has personified not only Egdon Heath, but also the existence of the human beings. The former wakes and listens when other creatures sleep. Its titanic form waits for some mishaps each and every night till the last crisis—final overthrow. Like the former, the later too is always a chief personage embodied in it.

The Vision of the cosmic absurdity—the gulf between man's longing for order and happiness along with eternal indifferent drift of things—projects a picture of the general human place and position. The main characters like Eustacia Vye and Clym Yeobright are always with a deep sense of boredom and unhappiness in its (Egdon Heath's) hollow track. Their condition—especially of Eustacia— is like the condition of Hamlet, the prince of Denmark, who always swings like a pendulum between the set conditions of "to be or not to be" (*Hamlet*. Act III, Sc. i. L. 55). Eustacia, the heroine of the novel, ceaselessly longs for going to Paris to have romance and luxury. It is the every reason why she marries Clym Yeobright, the protagonist of the novel, thinking him to be the only person to satisfy her dreams. But it is irony of her destiny and choice that her dreams are shattered. With illusion in heart, she remains dissatisfied with him. She does not want to live in such conditions and starts an extra marital affair with reckless Damon. It is her choice which brings doom not only to herself but also to Clym's mother and Damon Wildev as well. Such incidents suggest the existential thought that any desire to achieve happiness is finally for upend in the quandary of human condition. This is why Hardy writes: "It all seems a tissue of contrivances for checkmating any possibility of a happy issue for these two beings, symbols of humanity in the hands of some power against which it is a vain to contend" (*Hardy* 161).

Edmund Blunden writes in *The Return of the Nature* "He (Hardy) was working more passionately from his deeper nature, and his reading of earth" (*Edmund Blunden* 44). Both

Eustacia and Clym have deeper persuasion in the context of human existence which all is futile, meaningless, and purposeless. How and what is life on this blue planet is convinced well by Thomas Hardy in a poem entitled as “A Young Man’s Epigram on Existence”. In it he writes:

A senseless school where we must give

Our lives that we may learn to live!

A dolt is he who memorizes

Lessons that leave no time for prize. (Thomas Hardy 1886/ public-domain-poetry.com).

About the predicament of man’s existence— which engages the big questions related to man’s life, man’s suffering, and the hostility of the cosmos— on the title page of the novel *The Return of the Native*, he has depicted a quotation from John Keats which says that sorrow is universal. None can escape it as it is not bad, but dear and constant. He writes:

To sorrow

I bade good morrow

And though to leave her far away behind;

But cheerily, cheerily,

She loves me dearly;

She is so constant to me, and so kind,

I would deceive her, and so leave her,

But ah! She is so constant and so kind.

(A Quotation abstracted from Keats’ “The Ode to Sorrow in Endymion” on the title page of *the Return of the Native*)

Egdon Heath with its black soil and somber beauty—black beauty— is always unsympathetic and unkind to the mass who reside there. Representing the cosmic workings, it reminds to one and all that man is no more significant than a worm or an insect against its far-extending barrenness. It helps in revealing the bitter reality of the existence of human beings. Hardy has presented a confrontation between man and nature. How much intellectual and talented man becomes, yet s/he is unable to comprehend the nature/cosmos. Pigmy and feeble is man before it. Such is with the native of the Heath. They try to comprehend it but all ends in smoke. The black Heath continually does the blackish deed with them. It makes them puppet in its hands. They do,

what it wants. About Egdon Heath, in the opening chapter of the novel, Hardy symbolically describes it as a cosmos which remains silent and silently does its deeds against man's will, choice and action. What man purposes, it disposes. Those who hate it— Eustacia Vye, Damon Wildeve, and Mrs Yeobright— are undone, but those who love it—Diggory Venn, Thomasin, and Clym Yeobright— are without any harm. He writes:

It was at present a place perfectly accordant with man's nature— neither ghastly, hateful, nor ugly: neither common place, unmeaning, nor tame; like man, slighted and enduring; and with singularly colossal and mysterious in its swarthy monotony. As with some some persons who have long lived apart, solitude seemed to look out of its countenance. it had a lonely face, suggesting tragical possibilities (*Hardy 4*).

Cosmos is unchangeable and unchangeable are its rules such is with This Heath. The unchangeable features of the Heath reinforce its ability to resist any attempt to change its nature: "The Sea changed, the fields changed, the rivers, the villages, and the people changed, yet Egdon remained" (*Hardy 5*). Its dreadful appearance enhances the views of the native towards it. Its primitive nature seems to be an enemy of progress and development—civilization and modernism:

The untamable, Ishmaelish thing that Egdon now was it always had been. Civilization was its enemy; and ever since the beginning of vegetation its soil had worn the same antique brown dress, the natural and invariable garment of the particular formation. In its venerable one coat lay a certain vein of satire on human vanity in clothes. A person on heath in raiment of modern cut and colour has more or less an anomalous look. We seem to want the oldest and simplest human clothing where the clothing of the earth is so primitive (*Hardy 4*).

The leading characters of this novel are surrounded by the absurdities and enigmatic oddities of life. Its (Egdon Heath's) ways of working is as mysteriously as time, coincidence, destiny, irony, and society. Estacia Vye is the first character who first of all feels its absurdities and oddities, but she is helpless before its cruel hands. About her condition in the opening chapter of the novel, Hardy writes:

Eustacia Vye was the raw material of a divinity. On Olympus she would have done well with a little preparation. She had the passion and instincts which make a model goddess that is, those which make not quite a model woman. Had it been possible for the earth and mankind to be entirely in her grasp for a while, she had handled the distaff, the spindle, and the shears at her own free will, few in the world would have noticed the change of government. There would have been the same inequality of lot, the same heaping up of favors here, of contumely there, the same

generosity before justice, the same perpetual dilemmas, the same captious alteration of caresses and blows that we endure now (*Hardy 73*).

When one goes through the novel, one finds that when Clym returns from Paris, Eustacia pines for seeing him, but the cosmic forces which are beyond her control works differently. It is another thing that she is able to see him at last by playing a role in the mummers, and establishing a rapport with him, she finally succeeds in marrying him. But the cosmic forces constantly trigger her, and she is forced to be the victim of frustration helplessly and unwillingly. Clym's condition is also like her. He is also victim of cosmic forces. He can't bear his separation from his mother and later on her death. Again and again he tries to sort out the differences between Eustacia and his mother, but all in vain due to time and coincidence. It is chance and fate that when Mrs. Yeobright visits Clym to patch up her differences to Eustacia, he falls asleep and utters 'Mother' in his dream, but this word is overheard by his mother Mrs. Yeobright. The condition goes from bad to worse when Eustacia prevents her from entering the house. She thinks this prevention as the maneuvering of her son. Things become worst while returning with laden heart, she is bitten by a snake and dies enroute. About this mysterious working of the cosmic forces, Eustacia Vye feels guilty. She says: "Upon the shoulders of some indistinct, colossal Prince of the world of the world (who) had framed her situation and ruled her lot" (*Hardy, Return of the Native 351/352*). Like Eustacia, Clym also feels something like this when he becomes the victim of near-blindness which symbolizes deeper inner blindness. It is another thing that he thinks himself to be guilty of their death. He is thus posited to be the source of the cosmic power, but it (cosmic power) is too complex for him to comprehend as it engulfs the ignorant denizens of the heath without any rhyme and reason. According to Eustacia, she does her best to be a good woman, but her destiny is against her. To her, this world is ill conceived where she is to dwell. The cosmic mysteries which are beyond her control have injured, blighted, and crushed her. Like an existential man, she has become victim of existential crises. This is why she says:

How I have tried and tried to be a splendid woman, and how destiny has been against me!...I do not deserve my lot!...O, the cruelty of putting me into this ill conceived world! I was capable of much; but have been injured and blighted and crushed by things beyond my control! O, how hard it is of Heaven to devise such tortures for me, who have done no harm to heaven at all. (*Ernest Baker 37- Abstracted from Return of the Native*)

Hardy has not only personified the cosmic absurdities (mysteries) which engulf the denizens of the Heath, but also the existence which makes and mars them. It too has always been presented as a personage. About it Ernest A. Baker says:

The pictorial opening of the novel is famous. It introduces the chief character; for in Hardy's stories, Nature, the Earth, Existence, is always a personage, and that chief personage is embodied this time in Egdon Heath, the dark, immemorial environment whose influence control obscurely the lives and destinies of those who dwell contentedly amid its grossy wilderness or feel themselves cruelly out of their element there (*Baker 36*).

In this novel, no doubt, Nature- the Earth and Existence have their own existence. And a thing which has its existence performs various kinds of deed which may be good or bad which makes or mars the chief characters. It directly or indirectly affects them. Such is with the denizens of the moorland-the Heath. Those who are weak and try to comprehend it are affected by it mostly. Its first victim is Eustacia Vye. About her, Baker writes:

Eustacia Vye was the raw material of a divinity. She had the passions and instincts which make a model goddess, that is, those which make not quite a model woman. Shallow, sensuous, high-strung, a typical decadent, she is keenly aware so far as she herself is concerned, that she is a victim of the preserve dispensation of the things. Circumstances have put her in the wrong place; juxtaposition with the heath is the bane of her existence, and by that token everything is wrong (*Baker 37*).

Chance or time and coincidence, irony, and natural calamity are the hand of cosmic absurdity through which it does its blackish deeds. In the *Return of the Native*, chance and fate play a significant role. It is chance or time and coincidence that when Mrs Yeobright visits Clym for compromise, he was sleeping and uttering "Mother" in his dream. It is chance as well as irony of fate that Eustacia did not let her enter home consequently she went from there and a snake became the cause of her death. Natural calamity also plays a crucial role when the novel attains its climax. It brings three deaths successively as first of all dies Mrs. Yeobright, and later on Eustacia and Wildev. These deaths shake Clym's mind and soul. He feels guilty and this feeling of guilty is also the result of cosmic absurdities— the absurdity of individual experience.

Cosmic absurdity which is limited to actions and choices of human beings is also presented well in this novel. Whatever man does, does with his own choices and these choices depend on his/her will and time and coincidence. Good faith and Bad faith are also responsible for his/her actions. In this novel, Clym, a man of good faith, and Eustacia, a lady of bad faith, both suffer due to the cosmic absurdities which are out of their control. Both have their own aims and ambitions; their own anxieties; their own crises. When one observes Clym, one finds that he is a promising lad. He wishes to leave the world of diamonds in Paris with the aim of opening a school in Egdon Heath to serve the natives selflessly. He leaves Paris and settles near the Heath. It's pity that the semi-blindness, which is the result of over study, disables him from executing the educational

project. His affair and marriage with Eustacia is not successful. His maternal bond is also broken. All these mishaps suggest that all is the result of cosmic absurdities which make his life miserable, his condition pitiable, and his soul torn. About Clym, the novelist Thomas Hardy writes: “In consequence of this relatively advanced position, Yeobright might have been called unfortunate. The rural world was not ripe for him. A man should be only partially before his time: to be completely to the vanward in aspirations is fatal to fame” (Hardy 195). It is also with Eustacia. She can’t bear the loneliness of the Heath. To her it is her cross, her shame, and the cause of her death in future. The miserable condition of the major characters reminds a few words of William Shakespeare, the bard of Avon, who in his tragedy *King Lear* writes: “As flies to wanton boys are we to the gods; / they kill us for their sport” (Shakespeare, *King Lear*. Act IV, Sc. I, Lns. 35-37).

In short, it can be said that this cosmos is absurd because it has no inherent meaning except what man gives to it. Additionally, it gets its meaning through the thoughts and actions of sentience within it. It is inherently absurd without any absolute knowledge. Man is also its part so man’s existence has no inherent meaning of its own. Man tries to create personal meaning, as long as man retains ironic distance towards it. Such is chiefly with Eustacia and Mrs. Yeobright in this novel. Both try to create their personal meaning, but the cosmic absurdity through its various hands (fate, chance, natural calamity etc.) checks them. They get only death. Like Sisyphus, Clym Yeobright becomes the symbol of absurd existence without any fault of his own. Through the Egdon Heath, each and every chapter of this novel tells the tale of cosmic absurdity.

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